

Results

SI Events

- Overall, a steady decline over an 11-year time s
- Reduction of CLABSI compared to baseline days, $p = .04$)
- Significant (40%) CLA (4.39 vs 2.38/1000 line active intervention pha
- Maintenance of reduced sustainment phase CL